

FREQUENCY EFFECTS ON DELAMINATION CHARACTERISTICS OF LAMINATES WITH AND WITHOUT AN INTERLEAF

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ABSTRACT:

The effects of load frequency on delamination onset life and growth characteristics were investigated in the $(30,-30_2,30,90)_s$ IM6/3501-6 laminates with and without an interleaf. The interleaf used in this study was FM 300 of the American Cynamid Product and was placed at the interface between 30 and 90 plies.

Life of delamination onset is defined as the number of cycles at which the delaminated area is 3% of the total laminate area. The results indicate that in the baseline laminate the delamination life increases as loading frequency increases. In the interleaved laminates, the life increases as frequency increases at a lower load level. For both the laminates the delamination growth rates were found to increase with frequency, However, at higher load level, the trend was reversed. At the lower load level, the interleaved laminates have slower growth rate compared to the baseline laminate.

In fractographic analysis the interleaved laminate shows a greater number of hackles indicating a greater mode-II contribution to failure. Moreover as the frequency increases, the orientation of the hackles with the ply plane reduces. This suggests that the laminates subjected to a lower frequency shows greater ductile fracture patterns.

KEYWORDS: Delamination; Fatigue; Frequency Effects; Interleaf; Damage Tolerance; Durability.

INTRODUCTION

Load frequency was considered to have little effect on the fatigue life of metals. However, recent studies have shown that the fatigue life of thermoset and thermoplastic composites show varied frequency dependent response [1,2]. In their study with notched $(+45)_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates, Sun and Chan [3] found that when the temperature effect is negligible, the fatigue life was directly proportional to the load frequency. Saff [4] observed that the matrix dominated layups showed greater frequency dependence than the fiber dominant layups. Sun, et.al.[5] reported that for notched $(+45)_s$ IM6/PEEK laminates, the fatigue life decreased with increasing frequency even in the low frequency range. This behavior is opposite to that of epoxy-based composites. They

found that the fatigue life of PEEK thermoplastic composites was higher than the 3501-6 thermoset laminates in the lower frequency range but not in the higher frequency levels. The effect of frequency was also found to be dependent on the load level. Reifsnider, Stinchcomb and O'Brien [6] found that the fatigue life of both graphite/epoxy and boron/epoxy laminates increased with increasing frequency in the low frequency range while in the higher frequency level it decreased with increasing frequency.

In the above studies, the effect of frequency on the fatigue life of laminates with a hole has been studied. The fatigue life was defined as the total failure of the laminate. Little work has been done to study the effect of frequency on the free edge delamination.

Free edge problem has been widely used to study the characteristics of delamination in laminates. The concept of using an interleaf in laminates to improve the static and fatigue delamination behavior has been investigated [7]. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of load frequency on the delamination onset life and growth characteristics. The determination of delamination onset under fatigue loading requires continuous monitoring. However, continuous monitoring of a fatigue test is impractical. Subramanian and Chan [8] used a 5% delamination width of the coupon to define the onset to characterize fatigue behavior with good results. In this study the life of delamination onset is defined as the number of cycles at which the delaminated area is 3% of the total area of the laminate.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Coupons of the (30,-30₂,30,90)_s IM6/3501-6 graphite/epoxy laminate with and without an interleaf, FM300 were manufactured under the same curing procedure. The interleaf was placed at the 30/90 interface. This stacking sequence was chosen because this layup makes the laminate susceptible to delamination, thus allowing to study the growth behavior before the ultimate failure. Each coupon has 9 inch long and 1.5 inch wide and bonded with glass tabs. Coupon panels were carefully checked for voids by C-scan before cutting and for delamination by x-ray radiography after cutting. All tests were conducted on an MTS servo Hydraulic Testing System. The strains were measured using a 0.475" MTS clip gauge.

Static Test

Static test was used to determine the delamination-onset strength which was served the determination of the fatigue loading. All static tests were run under a constant stroke rate of 0.05"/min. One set each of both laminates was tested until the onset of visible delamination monitored by an optical microscope. The test was stopped when delamination occurred. The specimen was removed and the extent of damage was documented by dye-penetrant enhanced X-radiography. The variation of load and strain was recorded using a Hewlett-Packard X-Y plotter and a Nicolet Oscilloscope which was equipped with a computer disk drive. Another set of specimen was tested until total failure of the laminate. The ultimate tensile strength was calculated from the failure load obtained from these tests.

Static Delamination Growth Resistance Test

Growth resistance test were used to determine delamination resistance which will

be served to establish the growth model. Two specimen each from the baseline and interleaved laminates were tested to generate the delamination growth resistance curve. Each laminate was loaded to a specific load level and removed for x-radiographic examination to document the delamination size.

Fatigue Test

All fatigue tests were conducted under load control with a stress ratio $R = 0.1$. Three frequencies varying from 10,1,0.1 Hz were considered. The maximum stress is selected as a fraction of static onset of delamination strength. Once delamination was initiated, radiographs were made to document the damage at the specified number of cycles. The photographs were digitized using the software AUTOCAD to measure the percentage of the delaminated areas. The load-strain data were recorded in an X-Y plotter and stored in a floppy. During the test, temperature rise at the free edge was monitored. It was found to be negligibly small for all load and frequency levels used in this investigation.

Fractographic Investigation

One specimen of each test condition from both laminates was examined for fatigue morphology. In all the cases, the 90° ply fracture surface was used to compare the frequency effect and the effect of the introduction of an adhesive layer. A Cambridge Stereoscan 120 Scanning Electron Microscope was used to observe and document the fracture morphology in this investigation. The test samples were cut into small 0.5" x 0.25" pieces. The 90° ply fracture surface was pretreated and an accelerating voltage of over 20 Kv was used during this investigation. All the pictures were taken at low magnifications in the range between 1000x and 2000x.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Tests

Figure 1 shows the delamination onset stresses and the ultimate tensile strength for laminates with and without an interleaf. The results indicate that static delamination onset stress was found to increase by 11 % with the interleaved laminates. Figure 1 also shows a 11 % decrease in the ultimate tensile strength value due to the addition of the FM300 layer. This contradicts the trend observed by Chan et.al.[7] in the FM1000 interleaved laminate. In the FM1000 interleaved laminate, ultimate strength was increased by 20% compared to the strength in the baseline laminate.

Static Delamination Growth Resistance Test

The delamination growth resistance is measured by the strain energy required to grow a unit length of delamination at a given load level. Mathematically, it is defined [11] as

$$G_R = \frac{\sigma^2 t}{2 E} \left(1 - \frac{E^*}{E} \right)$$

where σ	=	applied stress
t	=	laminate thickness
E	=	laminate stiffness at any given load
E^*	=	laminate stiffness of fully delaminated laminate

The test data was fitted using an exponential curve as shown in Fig 2. It is seen that the value of delamination growth resistance is greater for the interleaved laminate.

Fatigue Tests

The delamination onset (3% delamination) was calculated for each specimen from the curve which was used to fit the data of the delaminated area and fatigue cycles. The average delamination onset for a particular frequency at a specific load level was calculated by averaging the delamination onset cycles for each specimen at that load and frequency.

Table 1 lists the test matrix and delamination onset life. In the baseline laminates, the increase in frequency from 1 Hz to 10 Hz results in an increase in the delamination onset cycles. For 1 and 0.1 Hz frequency loadings, the delamination onset life is higher for interleaved laminates under 80% and 75% of fatigue loads than for the baseline laminate.

The delamination growth rates for different frequencies versus strain energy release rate at maximum stress in the baseline and interleaved laminates are shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. The Poursartip's model [9] shown below was used to fit the data obtained in this study.

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \alpha \left(\frac{G_{max}}{G_R} \right)^\beta$$

These figures indicate that the delamination growth rate is greater for higher frequencies. The slope of the curve is also found to increase as the loading frequency was reduced. This implies that the delamination growth rate for lower frequency level is more load sensitive. At lower load levels, lower frequency loading results in lower growth rates. However at higher load levels, the growth rates become nearly equal for all frequencies and at very high load levels, the lower frequency loading may result in greater delamination growth rates. This could be due to the fatigue retardation effect resulting from the formation of large plastic zones at the delamination crack tip at lower frequency and load levels. However at higher load levels, the force driving the delamination crack could be sufficient to drive the delamination crack through the plastic zone. Once the crack has overcome this retardation effect, the lower frequency could result in more damage due to the effect of creep. A similar effect has been reported by Lee and Charentary [10].

Comparison of the delamination growth rates for the baseline and interleaved laminates are depicted in Figures 5 and 6. From these figures it is seen that the magnitude of delamination growth rate of the interleaved laminates are lower than those of the baseline laminates at a given load level. However, it was observed that the slope of the curve representing the delamination growth rate of the interleaved laminate was greater than that of the baseline laminate. This suggests that the higher loads and higher

frequencies could result in greater damage in the interleaved laminates.

Results of Fractographic Investigation

Figure 8 shows a comparison of the fracture surface of baseline and interleaved laminates subjected to static loading. The interleaved laminates show greater number of hackles indicating a mode II dominant failure. These observations are consistent with the finite element results which show a greater mode II contribution in the total strain energy release rates [7]. It also appears that the number of hackles and the orientation of the hackles with the ply plane is greater in the interleaved laminate. These results agree well with observations made by Bradley and Hibbs [11] where they reported an increase in the hackle orientation angle with increase in mode II loading.

Figure 9 shows the fractographs of both laminates subjected to 0.1 Hz, 1 Hz and 10 Hz frequency of loading respectively. For the baseline laminate, the orientation of the hackles with the ply reduces as the frequency of loading increases. The fracture morphology of laminates subjected lower frequency loading shows greater ductile fracture patterns. This is evidenced by the hackles being extended and having irregular fronts typical of shear and ductile failures. It was also observed that the fracture surface of the 0.1 Hz sample showed very few hackles compared to the other samples. This is indicative of greater degree of ductile deformation being involved during the failure of the laminates subjected to a lower frequency of loading.

A similar pattern was observed in the interleaved laminates as shown in Figure 10. A reduction in the orientation/angle of hackles with the ply plane was observed. A greater degree of ductility was seen in the failures of laminates subjected to lower frequency loading. As in the case of baseline laminates, the number of hackles were lesser in the laminates subjected to 0.1 Hz frequency loading.

A comparison of the failures at the same frequency in baseline laminates and interleaved laminates reveals that the orientation of hackles with the ply plane is greater in the interleaved laminates. This is similar to the behavior under static loading.

CONCLUSIONS

Several conclusions have been drawn from this study.

1. For the baseline laminates, the delamination onset life at 3 % of the damage size seems to increase as load frequency increases. For the interleaved laminates, the life tends to increase as frequency increases at lower load level.
2. For both laminates, the delamination growth rates were found to increase with frequency. However, at higher load level, the trend was reversed.
3. The delamination growth rate in laminates with an FM 300 interleaf was lower at low load level compared to the baseline laminates. However, at higher load levels, the growth rates seem not to depend on the frequency.
4. Fractographic analysis for both static and fatigue loading indicates that the introduction of FM 300 interleaf results in increased number of hackles and the inclination of the hackles with the ply plane, which indicates the dominant Mode II failure.
5. For both laminates, fractographic morphology shows that an increase in frequency results in decrease of ductility and hackle angle.

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REFERENCES

1. Reifsnider, K. L., Henneke, E. G., Stinchcomb, W. W. and Duke, J. C., " Damage Mechanics and NDE of Composite Laminates," in Mechanics of Composite Materials, Recent Advances, Z. Hashin and C.T. Herakovich, eds., 1983, pp. 399-420.
2. Bradshaw, F. J. and Wheeler, C., " The Influence of Gaseous Environment and Fatigue Frequency on the Growth of Fatigue Cracks in Some Aluminum Alloys," International Journal of Fracture Mechanics, Vol. 5, 1969, pp. 255-268.
3. Sun, C. T. and Chan, W. S., " Frequency Effect on the Fatigue Life of a Laminated Composite," Composite materials: Testing and Design (Fifth Conference), ASTM STP 674, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1979, pp. 418-430.
4. Saff, C. R., " Effect of Load Frequency and Lay-up on the Fatigue Life of Composites," Long-Term Behavior of Composites, ASTM STP 813, T.K.O'Brien, ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1983, pp. 78-91.
5. Sun, C. T., Dan Jumbo, E. and Zhou, S. G., " Load Frequency Effect on the Fatigue Life of IM6/APCII Thermoplastic Composite Laminates," Advances in Thermoplastic Matrix Composites, edited by Golan Newaz, ASTM STP 1044, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1989.
6. Reifsnider, K. L., Stinchcomb, W. W. and O'Brien, T. K., " Frequency Effects on a Stiffness Based Fatigue Failure Criterion in Flawed Composite Specimen," Fatigue of Filamentary Composite Materials, ASTM STP 636, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1977, pp. 171-184.
7. Chan, W. S., Rogers, C. and Aker, S., " Improvement of Edge Delamination Strength of Composite Laminates using Adhesive Layers," Composite materials: Testing and Design (Seventh Conference), ASTM STP 893, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1986, pp. 266-285.
8. Scriver, G.C. and Chan, W.S., " Effects of Stress Ratio on Edge Delamination Characteristics in Laminated Composites," To be presented in the 4th ASTM Symposium on Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture, May 1991.
9. Poursartip, A., " The Characterization of Edge Delamination Growth in Laminates under Fatigue Loading," Toughened Composites, ASTM STP 937, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1986, pp. 218-237.
10. Lee, J. R. and De Charentenay, E. X., " Short Holding Time Effect on Fatigue Behavior of Unnotched Graphite/Epoxy Laminates (± 45)_s," Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 23, Sept. 1989.

11. Hibbs, M. F. and Bradley, W. L., "Correlation Between Micromechanical Failure Processes and the Delamination Toughness of Graphite/Epoxy systems," Fractography of Modern Engineering Materials : Composites and Metals, ASTM STP 948, J.E. Masters and J.J.Au, eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1987, pp. 68-97.

Table 1: Test matrix and test results.

Laminate Type	$\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{dt}$	Frequency (Hz)	No. of Tests	Delamination Onset (Cycles)
Without an Interleaf	0.8	10	2	9976
		1	3	6598
		0.1	3	4591
	0.75	10	3	59096
		1	2	8254
	0.70	10	3	128094
1		2	59492	
With an Interleaf	0.80	10	3	7671
		1	4	12655
		0.1	4	14803
	0.75	10	4	21109
		1	5	17015
		0.1	2	43741
	0.70	10	5	138984
		1	4	59098

Fig.1 Comparison of delamination stress and ultimate strength of laminates with and without an interleaf.

Fig.2 Static delamination Resistance Curve.

Fig.3 Delamination growth rate for the baseline laminates at different frequencies.

Fig.4 Delamination growth rate for interleaved laminates at different frequencies.

Fig.5 Comparison of delamination growth rate of baseline and interleaved laminates at 10 Hz.

Fig.6 Comparison of delamination growth rate of baseline and interleaved laminates at 1 Hz.

Fig.7 Comparison of delamination growth rate of baseline and interleaved laminates at 0.1 Hz.

Fig.8 Comparison of fractographs of baseline and interleaved laminates under static load.

Fig.9 Comparison of fractographs of baseline laminates under fatigue at various frequencies.

Fig.10 Comparison of fractographs of interleaved laminates under fatigue at various frequencies.